

INFILTRATION OF FIBROUS PREFORM BY A LIQUID METAL : MODELIZATION OF THE PREFORM DEFORMATION

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SUMMARY : During Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) processing by injection or squeeze casting method, the fibrous preform can be damaged on account of high liquid injection pressure. In this paper, a one-dimensional numerical simulation of a liquid infiltration through a deformable preform is presented. First the physical model and resolution algorithm are described. Then some numerical results are presented : the influences of injection rate and capillary pressure on injection pressure and preform deformation are studied. Finally, a conclusion is given which presents possible developments and applications of this simulation in more realistic cases.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, processing, numerical simulation, deformable preform, Darcy equation.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) can be processed by methods involving liquid metal and fibrous preform, these methods are named either injection or squeeze casting : a sufficient pressure is imposed on a metal which flows through a fibrous preform placed inside a mold [1-3]. These methods are interesting for processing MMCs because they can be automated at a very rapid cadence, which supposes great Darcy velocities during the metal infiltration. High pressure is necessary to obtain such Darcy velocities depending on preform permeability and metal solidification conditions. Such high pressure may damage the preform before it is infiltrated by the metal.

Some studies presented theoretical or numerical models of infiltration and solidification of a pure metal in a fibrous preform [4, 5] : in these papers, it is shown that the injection pressure depends on thermal parameters of the metal and preform (*i.e.* volumic heat, conductivity, initial temperature) and injection parameters (injection rate, mold channel thickness). In another paper, the relation between permeability and solid metal fraction is studied through experimental tests [6] : during the infiltration of the preform, a fraction of liquid metal solidifies in the vicinity of the cold fibres, which reduces the porosity and consequently the permeability. In all these works, the preform was assumed to be infinitely stiff, so that no deformation was possible.

The aim of this paper is to present a one-dimensional numerical simulation of the infiltration of a liquid through a deformable preform. Only the preform deformation due to the liquid flow is considered, so that the heat transfer and metal solidification are not taken into account.

First, the physical model is presented and the resolution algorithm is described. Then some numerical results are presented, such as the influence of injection rate and capillary pressure on injection pressure. Finally, a conclusion is given which presents possible developments and applications of this simulation in more realistic problems taking into account heat transfer in two or three-dimensional geometry.

THE PHYSICAL MODEL AND RESOLUTION ALGORITHM

During the infiltration of a liquid metal in a fibrous preform, the viscous forces induce a stress field in the solid skeleton of the preform. Moreover, the capillary pressure, which is the minimum pressure of the liquid to infiltrate the preform, also induces a stress field which is superimposed to the field resulting from viscous forces. These stress fields induce a deformation field according to the deformation law of the preform, *e.g.* elastic law or plastic law, viscoplastic law... Even if the original preform exhibits an homogeneous permeability, the deformation of the preform, which is not homogeneous, induces an heterogeneous permeability field. This heterogeneous permeability field occurs as soon as the liquid infiltrates the porous preform, and hinders the liquid flow. The permeability can be reduced to values near to 0, so that infiltration can become impossible.

In this section, the physical problem is presented with the geometry and conditions. Then the equations which govern the physical phenomenon are given, and the numerical algorithm is described.

Geometry, initial, boundary conditions

For the application to the MMCs processing, it would be necessary to take into account the thermal transfers and the permeability decrease due to partial solidification of the metal [6]. But in this preliminary study, we only simulate the physical behaviour of the preform during its impregnation by a liquid.

A fibrous preform is placed inside a mold (Fig. 1). A homogeneous constant Darcy velocity is imposed at the left boundary, which displaces the liquid front in the preform. It is assumed that there is no friction between the preform and mold walls, so that the "preform + liquid" group supports forces which are balanced at the right boundary of the preform : physically, it can be represented a grid which bears the preform at the right boundary. In the unsaturated area of the preform, the pressure is assumed to be constant and equal to 0. Besides, it can be imposed a capillary pressure at the liquid front.

Fig 1 : *Geometry and boundary conditions during the infiltration of the liquid in the preform*

Such a problem is a mono-dimensional problem. Moreover, given the characteristic times of the involved physical phenomena, it can be assumed that there is an instantaneous mechanical

equilibrium. As a consequence, it is possible to solve the steady state mechanical equations at any moment, only the liquid front position directly depends on time.

Equations

To describe the infiltration of a liquid in a deformable fibrous preform, it is necessary to solve the equations which govern the fluid flow and preform deformation.

Deformation of the preform

It is supposed that the mechanical behaviour of the preform is elastic. Moreover, as there is no friction between the preform and the mold walls, it can be assumed that the deformation of the preform is proportional to the compression stress.

When the deformation reaches a maximum value, no more deformation is possible whatever the value of the compression stress : this behaviour is schematically described in Fig. 2. It is assumed that this behaviour law is perfectly reversible.

Fig. 2 *Mechanical behaviour of the preform*

In this work, the mechanical behaviour is very simple but in the steps to come, it will be necessary to choose a more representative law for the preform behaviour.

Relation between compression stress and permeability

Before any liquid infiltration, the porosity is homogeneous in the preform and equal to Φ_0 . When the preform is compressed, the porosity decreases : therefore it is possible to link the compression stress or the deformation to the porosity Φ .

On the other hand, the local permeability \bar{K} of the preform depends on its porosity Φ : the chosen relation between permeability and porosity is the classical Kozeny-Carman law [7] :

$$K = \frac{\phi^3}{5S_0^2(1-\phi)^2} \quad (1)$$

with S_0 the specific surface of the porous medium.

Liquid flow equations

In the fibrous preform, the liquid flow obeys the continuity equation (2) :

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (2)$$

and the Darcy law presented as follows when neglecting the gravitation forces (3) :

$$V = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

In these equations, V is the Darcy filtration velocity, P is the pressure, \bar{K} is the permeability, and μ the dynamic viscosity of the liquid.

Below the liquid front, in the unsaturated area of the preform, the pressure is assumed to be equal to 0. At the liquid front, there is a pressure discontinuity which is equal to the capillary pressure P_c [7].

As defined here, the problem can be solved from the Darcy equation with the following assumptions :

- i) the study domain is the liquid saturated area of the preform ;
- ii) at the left boundary, *i.e.* at the injection side, a constant Darcy velocity is imposed ;
- iii) at the right boundary, *i.e.* at the liquid front, a pressure condition is imposed, corresponding to the capillary pressure P_c .

To take into account the deformation of the preform and the conservation of both solid and liquid, a liquid volume production term is added in Darcy equation [8] : when the preform expands a sink term appears, but when the preform is reduced a source term appears.

Numerical algorithm

The schematic physical and numerical algorithm is given in Fig. 3. At time t , the liquid front position is known (Fig. 3a).

The pressure field in the liquid saturated area of the preform can be computed : the Darcy law is solved in this study domain with capillary pressure as a condition at the right boundary and constant Darcy velocity at the left boundary (Fig. 3b). In the liquid, the pressure obeys the Darcy law and it decreases from the injection pressure to the capillary pressure.

The solid skeleton of the preform bears viscous and capillary forces : these forces are balanced by a stress field which is a "complement" of the pressure field in the liquid (see Fig. 3c and 3b) : in the right section of the preform, there is a maximum which corresponds to the stress supported by the grid.

Corresponding to the stress field, a deformation field can be calculated according to the mechanical behaviour of the preform (Fig. 3d). This deformation field implies new porosity field, local changes in the space step dimensions, and liquid "production" as presented above.

From the porosity field, the Kozeny-Carman law allows to calculate new permeability field (Fig. 3e).

Through this description, it is evident that the preform deformation and the liquid transfer are not independent. The numerical method used to solve this problem is a fixed point method with iterative calculations of the different parameter fields until convergence (Fig. 3).

When the convergence is reached, the liquid front is displaced, the new parameter fields (permeability, liquid "production", space step dimensions,...) are input, and a new calculation sequence for time $t + \Delta t$ is led (Fig 3).

NUMERICAL RESULTS

A software was written based on the algorithm described above. In this section, the numerical and physical parameters are presented, then some examples are described, and finally the influences of the Darcy velocity and capillary pressure are shown.

Numerical and physical parameters

The sensibility of the solution was tested as a function of different numerical parameters, which allows to optimise the calculation. The numerical results presented below were obtained with the following parameters (when a parameter is defined as "initial", that means that it can vary during the infiltration).

Fig. 3 *Physical and numerical model of the infiltration of a fibrous preform by a liquid*

- For the mono-dimensional geometry, we have :
 - initial preform length = 1 m ;
 - number of space step = 50 ;
 - initial space step dimension = 0.02 m.
- The fibrous preform parameters are :
 - initial porosity = 0.9 ;
 - initial permeability = 10^{-7} m^2 ;
 - capillary pressure = from 0 to 10^5 Pa ;
 - linear relation between stress and deformation ;
 - minimum length of the preform = 0.3 initial length.
- For the liquid, the parameters are :
 - Darcy velocity = from 0.01 to 0.1 m s^{-1} ;
 - dynamic viscosity = 1 Pa s .

The aim of this preliminary study is to propose and test a numerical method and show the influences of some parameters on the liquid flow, so the used parameters are not representative of an actual impregnation.

Examples of infiltration simulations

First, the infiltration of a non-deformable preform by a liquid is simulated, with a capillary pressure equal to 0. In this example, the preform is not compressed, so its length and permeability are constant. In the liquid, the pressure is a linear function of the distance x from the injection boundary, and this pressure increases as the liquid front progresses because the infiltration length increases (Fig. 4) : the parameter i which defines each line of the figure corresponds to the position of the liquid front (node number). At $x = 0$, *i.e.* at the injection boundary, the calculated pressure is the injection pressure required to keep a constant Darcy velocity of the liquid.

Fig. 4 *Infiltration of a non deformable preform by a liquid ($V = 0.01 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) ; Evolution of the pressure field during the infiltration*

In Fig. 5a, it is shown that the preform length is constant whatever the position of the liquid front. It is possible to represent the injection pressure as a function of the position of the liquid front (Fig. 5b) : this relation is linear because the permeability is constant and consequently the injection pressure depends linearly on the length of the liquid saturated preform, *i.e.* the position of the liquid front.

Fig. 5 *Infiltration of a non deformable preform by a liquid ($V = 0.01 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) a) preform length vs liquid front position ; b) injection pressure vs liquid front position*

In the second example, the preform is assumed to be deformable and the capillary pressure equal to 0, then the evolution of the pressure field during the infiltration is more complex (Fig. 6) :

i) at the beginning of the infiltration, the pressure field is similar to that of non deformable preform since the preform is not very deformed and the permeability is close to the original permeability ;

ii) from the position of the liquid front corresponding to $i = 30$ and from $x = 300$ mm, the pressure variation is greater and linear, which means that, in this area, the preform reaches its maximum reduction, *i.e.* its minimum permeability, so that the pressure gradient is higher.

Fig. 6 Infiltration of a deformable preform by a liquid ($V = 0.01 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) ;
Evolution of the pressure field during the infiltration

The corresponding relations presenting the preform length and injection pressure as functions of the liquid front position are given in Fig. 7a - b for the Darcy velocity equal to 0.01 ms^{-1} .

For the evolution of the preform length during the infiltration, it is observed that the Darcy velocity equal to 0.1 ms^{-1} is great enough to induce a maximum reduction in a great fraction of the preform : so the length of about 300 mm is obtained very quickly after the beginning of the infiltration.

The evolution of the injection pressure involves two phases :

i) at the beginning of the infiltration there is a weak variation of the injection pressure ;

ii) as soon as the maximum deformation of the preform is reached, *i.e.* the minimum permeability, the influence of the entirely deformed area of the preform is predominant and the injection pressure seems to vary linearly.

Influence of the Darcy velocity on the injection pressure and preform length

Figures 7a and b present the influence of the Darcy velocity on the liquid flow.

For great Darcy velocities the reduction of the porous preform is maximum from very small infiltration lengths and for a great fraction of the preform length (Fig. 7a). When the deformation reaches its maximum, the permeability is very low which implies great pressure gradient, and consequently a great part of the relation between the injection pressure and the infiltration length is linear (Fig. 7b).

For low Darcy velocities, for example 0.01 m s^{-1} , the maximum deformation is obtained later, after about 300 mm are infiltrated (Fig. 7a), and the linear part of the figure 7b is much smaller (it is more apparent in fig.8b - capillary pressure $P_c = 0$ - in which the scale is more precise). Moreover, the final length after entire infiltration is greater than for higher Darcy velocities.

Fig. 7 Influence of the Darcy velocity on the liquid flow
 a) preform length vs liquid front position ; b) injection pressure vs liquid front position

Influence of the capillary pressure on the injection pressure and preform length

Figures 8a and b present the influence of the capillary pressure on the liquid flow.

For capillary pressures between 0 and 10^4 Pa, the morphologies of the relations between the preform length and the infiltrated length are similar, according to what was explained previously (Fig. 8a). On the contrary, for a capillary pressure equal to 10^5 Pa, the preform expands until it reaches its final length : on account of the high capillary pressure, before any infiltration by the liquid, the entire preform length supports such a high stress that the deformation is maximum ; when the liquid infiltrates the preform, the infiltrated part of the preform does not support any longer the stress from capillary pressure but only that from viscous forces, which implies a diminution of the deformation (this is due to the perfectly reversible elastic law chosen for the mechanical behaviour of the preform).

The relations between the injection pressure and the infiltrated length are easily explained for the capillary pressures only shift graphs from the no capillary pressure graph (Fig. 8b).

Fig. 8 Influence of the capillary pressure on the liquid flow
 a) preform length vs liquid front position ; b) injection pressure vs liquid front position

CONCLUSIONS

This simplified model allows a qualitative analysis of the influence of the preform deformation on the infiltration phenomenon : some infiltration defects experimentally observed can be explained thanks to this model.

The simulation of a preform infiltration by a liquid metal will imply different further numerical studies.

- Extension to bi or three-dimensional geometry from this mono-dimensional approach : the problem of displacement of the free boundary liquid front has to be solved, with the consequences on the mechanical preform deformation.
- Resolution of the heat transfer equation coupled to the liquid mass transfer equation : this problem was already solved [5], but in this case it is necessary to take into account the preform deformation.

Finally, it is important to underline that the quality of a numerical simulation depends on the pertinence of the input physical parameters ; it implies important experimental and metrological studies, especially concerning the mechanical behaviour of a preform partially saturated by solid metal...

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